

THE CHARM OF MEMORY

EXAMINING NOSTALGIC EXPERIENCE FROM A DESIGN PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

Nostalgia, as both a social phenomenon and subjective experience, plays a significant role in product experience, consumer preference and human-product/brand relationships. Despite frequent mention and use, relatively little explicit knowledge of this topic has been generated in relation to design. This paper therefore investigates nostalgic experience from a design perspective. Firstly, it proposes a heuristic model for explaining the underlying process of design-evoked nostalgic experience. Secondly, in order to provide a comprehensive understanding of the experience, it analyses nostalgia from three distinct product experience levels (*experience of meaning, aesthetic experience and emotional experience*) and highlights the relationship between nostalgic experience and memory retrieval (*explicit memory and implicit memory*). It then examines the influential factors of nostalgic experience from two perspectives: (1) the user and context; (2) the product and interaction. Finally, nostalgia is placed in a wider context in relation to *familiarity* and *novelty* within the overarching research field of “*Design and Memory*”. The ethical dimension of nostalgia is also addressed.

Keywords: Affective Design, Nostalgic Experience, Heuristic Model

INTRODUCTION

There is a growing interest amongst both design practitioners and researchers to understand design-related human experience, especially in the more affective aspects. Recent investigations into design-related experiences have helped practitioners to understand target users holistically and perhaps also inspired them in the process, whilst significantly expanding the boundary of the design discipline. Desmet and Hekkert (2007), for example, have

developed a framework for general product experience, whilst some specific types of experience, such as pleasure (e.g. Jordan, 2000) and playfulness (e.g. Arrasvuori, Boberg & Korhonen, 2010), have been studied as important concepts within the design field.

Perhaps surprisingly, nostalgia, a fundamental human experience which is closely related to design, has long been neglected in the design research field. However, in a less formal academic context, nostalgia is a relatively common design influence in areas such as advertising, fashion design and ‘retro’ products. In reality, many new products with retrospective visual elements (e.g. Pottery Barn’s furniture, and the Volkswagen New Beetle) are launched every year, consciously aiming to evoke consumers’ or users’ nostalgic experiences, often to enable companies to differentiate themselves from their rivals, attract specific consumer groups, and ultimately to achieve more ambitious sales. In addition, many designers have acquired design inspiration from historic iconic or everyday objects, drawn from both global or local cultures (e.g. Louise Filli in the US and Alan Chan in Hong Kong). On the other hand, paradoxically the term nostalgia has often been viewed as a taboo word by some ‘mainstream’ designers perhaps because of its sentimental associations and also because of the modernist dictat that designers should always look to the future instead of the past. These negative connotations might also be the reason why so little scholarly research has examined the nostalgic experience from a design perspective. But this lack of valid knowledge shouldn’t prevent nostalgia from constituting an important human experience, a social phenomenon and also the basis of a potential design strategy. Thus the creation of more explicit and reliable design knowledge on this topic will broaden our understanding of users and also improve its

planned application as an aid to designing better product/brand experiences.

In a study currently being undertaken by the authors of this paper, we are trying to understand firstly what nostalgic experience is; and secondly how nostalgic experience is evoked by design outcomes (designed artefacts, interactions or systems). Psychology has already played a crucial role in the study of human experience and therefore, existing psychological studies on memory and nostalgia form the theoretical basis of the current study. In addition, the fields of sociology and business studies have also contributed related knowledge on nostalgic experience, which offer further design insights. On the basis of this broad literature review, a heuristic model is proposed which illustrates the underlying process resulting in design-evoked nostalgic experience.

NOSTALGIA AND DESIGN

A HEURISTIC MODEL FOR DESIGN-EVOKED NOSTALGIC EXPERIENCE

Designers cannot design experience but only design for experience, because ‘experience is not a property of the product but the outcome of human-product interaction’ (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007:63). The type of experience elicited by specific kinds of product is influenced by four determinants: (1) the product, (2) the user(s), (3) the interactive process and (4) the context; and only two of these determinants (product and interaction) can exert design influence directly. As a result, when designing for a particular experience, initially designers often study and attempt to understand the experience, user(s) and context, then to identify and create the most appropriate design elements, as well as constructing a positive interaction mode based on an empathic understanding of the user(s) (Koskinen, Battarbee & Mattelmäki, 2003). A similar process for engaging nostalgic experience within the design process can also be envisaged. Based on this idea and the importance of memory retrieval in nostalgic experience, a heuristic model for explaining the

Figure 1. A heuristic model for design-evoked nostalgic experience

underlying process of design-evoked nostalgic experience is proposed (Figure 1). Firstly a clearer definition of nostalgia is required.

WHAT IS NOSTALGIA?

References to nostalgia originate in ancient history and its meaning can be traced back to literature as early as the writings of Homer, Hippocrates and Caesar (Havlena & Holak, 1991; Wildschut, Sedikides, Arndt, & Routledge, 2006; Sedikides, Wildschut, Arndt & Routledge, 2008). Nostalgia is also ubiquitous but when it was first conceptualised by Swiss physician Johannes Hofer in medical terms, it was believed to be a mental disease that shared the same meaning as homesickness and at that time was associated with Swiss soldiers (Hofer, 1688/1934). These narrow definitions of nostalgia existed till the beginning of twentieth century. However, more contemporary researchers have produced meaningful evidence to distinguish nostalgia from homesickness (Bellelli & Amatulli, 1997; Wildschut et al., 2006) and considered nostalgia to be a valid fundamental human experience which crosses cultural, social, economic and age-related boundaries.

Like many other complex and controversial psychological phenomenon, it is still difficult to arrive at a well accepted definition of nostalgia. In this paper, we are not therefore endeavouring to offer a perfect definition, either in general terms or from a specific design perspective, but instead presenting some popular definitions and parameters of nostalgia derived from existing literature (Table 1). By doing so, we hope to offer a more comprehensive understanding of the concept of nostalgia for design purposes. To accomplish this, the framework of product experience which distinguishes three types of product experience (*aesthetic experience*, *experience of meaning* and *emotional experience*) developed by Desmet and Hekkert (2007) is used as the primary vehicle for analysis.

Inevitably nostalgia is an experience which is evoked through memory retrieval, including *explicit memory* (e.g. recalling a personal anecdote) and *implicit memory* (e.g. developing an aesthetic preference). Explicit memory ‘involves conscious recollection of previous experiences’, it is ‘typically assessed with

recall and recognition tasks that require intentional retrieval of information from a specific prior study episode’. In contrast, implicit memory is an unintentional, non-conscious form of retention, and ‘it is assessed with tasks that do not require conscious recollection of specific episodes’ (Schacter 1992: 559). According to these psychological precepts, it can be argued that both explicit and implicit memory retrieval lead to a meaning level and aesthetic level of nostalgic experience respectively.

“A positively toned evocation of a lived past”	Davis, 1979:18
“Nostalgia is memory with the pain removed. The pain is today”	Lowenthal, 1985: 8
“A wistful mood that may be prompted by an object, a scene, a smell, or a strain of music”	Belk, 1990: 670
“A positively valenced complex feeling, emotion, or mood produced by reflection on things (objects, persons, experiences, ideas) associated with the past”	Holak & Havlena, 1998: 218
“A sentimental or bittersweet yearning for an experience, product, or service from the past”	Baker & Kennedy, 1994: 169
“An emotional state in which an individual yearns for an idealized or sanitized version of an earlier time period”	Stern, 1992: 11
“A preference (general liking, positive attitude or favourable effect) towards experiences associated with objects (people, places or things) that were more common (popular, fashionable or widely circulated) when one was younger (in early adulthood, in adolescence, in childhood or even before birth)”	Holbrook & Schindler 2003: 108
“A disproportionately positive emotion, with bittersweet elements.”	Sedikides, Wildschut & Baden, 2004: 204

Table 1. Definitions of Nostalgia

Nostalgia as Experience of Meaning

As we can see from the definitions, nostalgia is generally considered to be a mood, feeling, emotion or more generally as an affective state that involves explicit memory retrieval, through which people can experience meaning (personal or cultural) and which in turn results in a complex emotional experience. For example, one of the authors recently bought a pair of Chinese *Warrior* shoes (Figure 2), which were the most popular basketball shoe models in his home country between the 1950s and the 1990s, but which had rapidly almost disappeared since the late 1990s. The author owned one pair of *Warrior* shoes during his childhood and adolescence, and so did his parents. When encountering the *Warrior* shoes again in a local store several months ago, they vividly reminded the author of his childhood, so he bought them without hesitation. He then called some close old friends to have a reunion and show them the shoes, during which these friends all recalled their childhood anecdotes about the *Warrior* shoes and expressed great excitement. In effect, a symbolic meaning had been attached to the shoes representing their various childhoods.

Figure 2. The *Warrior* shoes owned by one of the authors

Nostalgia as an Aesthetic Experience

Considering the *Warrior* shoes as another kind of example: When the author stepped out of the store wearing the shoes, putting the symbolic meaning aside, he realised that he actually felt that they looked very attractive but he did not remember having such a strong liking for the appearance of the shoes during his childhood. Thus nostalgia can also be considered as an aesthetic preference for objects which can provide people with feelings of continuity, familiarity and security. Zajonc's mere exposure theory noted that the feeling of liking an object increases with repeated exposure (Zajonc, 1968), and Bornstein's meta-analysis (1989) to a great

extent verified Zajonc's hypothesis in concluding that there is a positive relationship between exposure frequency and aesthetic preference for the stimuli. The mere exposure effect has been interpreted as an implicit memory phenomenon by many psychologists (Schacter, 1987; Seamon et al., 1995; Squire, 1992). In other words, the particular aesthetic preference or taste results from the unconscious retrieval of implicit memory. Schindler and Holbrook (1993) considered the formation of nostalgic preference to be a result of the joint actions of both mere exposure and critical period. There is often a critical period (usually the stages of childhood, adolescence and young adulthood; the times in a person's life that are most influential) in the development of a person's tastes or preferences for products, and a heavy exposure to products during one's critical and early periods of influence is very likely to result in a life-long fondness for a product.

Nostalgia as an Emotional Experience

Despite perceived negative connotations, nostalgia is believed to be a "joyous" experience (Kaplan, 1987). In terms of Sedikides, Wildschut and Baden's (2004) views especially, the affective structure of nostalgia is a hybrid of both negative (e.g. feeling of loss) and positive emotions, but its nature is disproportionately positive. Positive expressions (e.g. love, warmth, gratitude, joy, elation and tenderness) are much more frequently linked with nostalgia by people than negative ones (Sedikides et al., 2004). There is also a strong tendency to filter out negative information in memory and retain only the positive (Davis, 1979, Belk, 1990; Havlena & Holak 1991; Holak & Havlena 1992; Stern 1992; Lyon & Colquhoun 1999). Consequently, nostalgia is usually associated with affectively charged autobiographical memories which are idealized and sanitized, and therefore 'the past is always better than the present, even when objective conditions suggest otherwise' (Meyers, 2009: 738).

Nostalgia, as an emotion, is thought to service several important psychological functions. Davis (1979, p. 31) described nostalgia as a psychological tool that we 'employ in the never ending work of constructing, maintaining, and reconstructing our

identities'. Furthermore, according to a series of recent empirical studies, psychologists have expanded the understanding of the functionality of nostalgia, arguing that nostalgia 'generates positive affect, elevates self-esteem, fosters social connectedness, and alleviates existential threat'. (Sedikides, Wildschut, Arndt & Routledge, 2008: 307). Because of these functions, the associations between nostalgia and human well-being, at both psychological and physical levels, are predicted, although supportive empirical research has not yet been conducted.

As discussed above, we consider that the *meaning level* of nostalgic experience involves *explicit memory* retrieval whilst the *aesthetic level* of nostalgic experience involves *implicit memory* retrieval. Both these levels of nostalgic experience can result in positive *emotional experience*.

THE USER AND CONTEXT

Age

Age is highly relevant to nostalgic experience as it is generally believed that people feel nostalgic more easily and frequently when they are older, although empirical data has shown that nostalgia is a phenomenon that could happen across a variety of age profiles. In addition, as a result of constant social and technological change, each generation or cohort (e.g. Generation X and Generation Y) grows up within distinctive social, political and technological contexts (Schuman and Scott, 1989) and forms particularly enduring preferences for products during its youth phase (Holbrook & Schindler, 1996). As an analogue of the phenomenon of imprinting (Lorenz 1951), the impact of early experience on nostalgic taste and age-related preference peaks for many product types (e.g. pop music and automobiles) have been studied (Holbrook & Schindler, 1989; 1994). We therefore consider that age is the primary determinant that affects nostalgic experience. Studying target product user groups as different cohorts (age-related segmentations) may encourage designers to trace back to an appropriate historical period and locate the most relevant design elements that might be employed to enhance user nostalgic experience when appropriate.

Gender

Gender difference is another factor that should be considered when designing for nostalgic experience. It has been reported that men tend to experience nostalgia through objects of action (e.g. vehicles), whereas women are more frequently inclined to consider objects of contemplation (e.g. textiles) a source of memories (Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton, 1981). Schindler and Holbrook's study (2003) also shows that females appear not to prefer the car styles of their youth, but male subjects do. In a previous study conducted by one of the authors (Xue, 2008), the different responses towards the film and toy 'Transformers' between Chinese males and females in the same cohort were observed. The male group showed much more intensive interest in and nostalgic reaction towards the Transformers than their female counterparts. Thus, designers should expect significant gender differences in the types of product or design elements that evoke nostalgic experience, although clearly there is a danger in reinforcing and repeating gender stereotyping, if this is not related to current user preferences and cultural contexts.

Psychographics

Psychographic factors, such as individual personality (extraversion or neuroticism) and attitudes toward past or nostalgia proneness, can also influence the evocation and enjoyment of nostalgic experience (Holbrook & Schindler, 1996; Barrett, 2010). For example, even within the same age cohort, of two male users, one may enjoy more nostalgic experience than another because he has a more positive attitude towards the past. Systematic measurement of the potential to experience nostalgia, such as the *Nostalgia Index* (Holbrook & Schindler, 1996) and the *Southampton Nostalgia Scale* (Routledge et al. 2008) have been developed in both business and psychological fields. These tools may be adapted and used by designers or design researchers in the future to measure an individual's general predisposition to nostalgia.

The Affective State

As mentioned previously, the affective state (e.g. mood) of the user also determines the degree of nostalgic experience. It has been discovered that

people experiencing certain uncomfortable affects (e.g. loneliness and anxiety) are more likely to desire objects that can elicit nostalgic experience than those who are generally experiencing a positive affect. The reason may reside in nostalgia's function of providing positive feelings and counteracting negative affective states. Nostalgia 'by being a stock of positive feelings, can ward off external threat or distressing thoughts.' (Sedikides, Wildschut & Baden, 2004: 210)

The Nostalgia Context

The general context of nostalgia involves two main issues: when and where. Davis (1979) claims that nostalgia is more desirable when such feelings as fear, discontent, anxiety, and uncertainty are prevalent. To some individuals, threatening or stressful stimuli, such as leaving home, getting divorced or becoming unemployed, may lead to such feelings. In broader societal terms, we might therefore expect a boom in nostalgia following significant social and economic transitions. Taking (mainland) China as an example, after implementing 30 years of reform and an opening-up policy, and 20 years of transition from a planned to a market economy, a resulting and important trend associated with collective behaviour in contemporary China is experiencing historically-rooted collective nostalgia, especially for those urban dwellers born in the 1980s who experienced particularly specific, collective experiences at an influential age (Xue & Woolley, 2009). Similar trends have also been reported in many former Eastern Bloc countries. New products incorporating historical influences which can trigger recall and enable people to re-experience positive memories in their childhood or adolescence are popular in these countries (e.g. Glavproduct in Russia, Tisza shoes in Hungary, Ampelmann in Germany; Xue & Woolley, 2009).

In addition, it appears that nostalgic experience would be more appreciated within the leisure context than the intensive goal-achieving context. For example, a bicycle which could evoke nostalgic experience, in most cases, is used for the casual cycling, whereas racing bicycles with futurist high-tech aesthetics may be preferred for competitions (Roy, 1992). Similarly, in a biochemical laboratory

for example, the nostalgic value of the furniture is less likely to be enjoyed than furniture in a home environment.

Whether nostalgic experience can be evoked by specific stimuli or design influences may also depend on cultural and geographical location. For example, the Commodore 64 computer was very popular as an 8-bit home computer in the USA and some European countries during the 1980s. Taking the original visual design of the Commodore 64, a fully functioning PC incorporating the latest technology was launched in May 2011. This is identified with a fast growing nostalgic cultural trend associated with the Commodore 64 and can be evidenced through many US and EU based websites and forums. Reasonably, we should not necessarily expect such a trend in China, simply because there was no Commodore 64 model marketed in the China during the 1980s, and therefore the name and appearance of the Commodore 64 have no apparent nostalgic meaning for Chinese users although of course, some may still like it today, if only because of their interest in exploring and experiencing the esoteric historic and cultural influences behind the machine.

PRODUCT AND INTERACTION

Sensory Inputs as the Triggers for Nostalgic Experience

Although humans can use all their senses to experience and interact with objects, it is generally believed that vision is the dominant sensory modality (Fenko, Schifferstein, & Hekkert, 2010). The idea of vision as the most important sensory modality is shared by both consumers and designers and when individuals are asked which sensory modality they would be most unwilling to lose, vision is the majority response (Schifferstein, 2006). For designers, visualization is considered a key competence. To some extent, this importance of visual thinking in the design discipline may well have restricted the growth of design knowledge related to other sensory modalities and this may apply equally to designing for nostalgic experience. Evoking nostalgic experience may simply mean 'looking old and this may be a consensus among design practitioners no matter whether they support or

oppose designing for nostalgic experience. One additional consideration is how to evoke nostalgic experience through alternative triggers, perhaps because too many products in the market simply recreate a vintage appearance without any new creative interpretation of the past.

One important fact that designers should perhaps absorb is that in terms of memory retrieval, other sensory modalities are worth considering and may sometimes result in unexpected and preferable effects. Hearing a song which was popular during one's adolescence could revive autobiographical memories and evoke relatively strong nostalgic experience. The sound is not necessarily a melody but need to be particular and be able to offer a feeling of familiarity. For example, the sound of a Polaroid instant camera ejecting the photo sheet is very likely to have a particular meaning for long term Polaroid users who frequently used the instant camera in their everyday lives decades ago and may have discarded it since the digital camera predominated.

Many psychologists emphasize the special capacity of smell (sometimes along with taste) to trigger vivid, emotionally charged memory and nostalgic experience (Chu & Downes, 2000). Hinton and Henley (1993) compared reactions to visual, lexical and olfactory stimuli, and found that odours elicited the most affective reactions. Proust (1922/1960) described a vivid retrieval of his childhood memory and nostalgic experience elicited by his olfaction and gestation, and this text has been conceptualized by psychologists as "Proustian Phenomenon".

"And soon, mechanically, weary after a dull day with the prospect of a depressing morrow, I raised to my lips a spoonful of the tea in which I had soaked a morsel of the cake. No sooner had the warm liquid, and the crumbs with it, touched my palate than a shudder ran through my whole body, and I stopped, intent upon the extraordinary changes that were taking place. An exquisite pleasure had invaded my senses...The taste was that of the little crumb of madeleine which on Sunday mornings at Combray (because on those mornings I did not go out before church-time), when I went to

say good day to her in her bedroom, my aunt Léonie used to give me, dipping it first in her own cup of real or of lime-flower tea...The sight of the little madeleine had recalled nothing to my mind before I tasted it..." (P. 58)

The smell of Play-Doh is another good example as the modelling compound has been popular among children in the US and global market for decades. A considerable number of adults had their happy childhood experiences associated with the special odour of Play-Doh, and it has been selected by Americans born after the 1950s as one of the most important smells that frequently evoke feelings of nostalgia (Hirsch, 2006).

Operational and Social Interactions as triggers of Nostalgic Experience

Nostalgic experience could also be derived from interactions, including both operational interactions and social interactions, particularly as interaction design has become one of the key topics in the design field. The development of digital technology made designers realise that their job is no longer about designing beautiful and useful artefacts alone, but is also concerned with addressing people's interactions with manmade objects or systems (Moggridge, 2007). Designing interactions may thus provide designers with a new source of inspiration for the triggers of nostalgic experience.

The term operational interaction refers here to the way people use or operate one product. If we think about our childhood, adolescence or simply 20 years ago, it is easy to understand how significantly the everyday products we use have changed. The progress of digital technology has forced many individuals to keep learning new ways to operate novel everyday products and develop new patterns of behaviour at the same time. For example, before the 1990s, the wired telephone with a dial face was dominant in China. Chinese urban dwellers used to interact daily with dial phones, although one telephone was often shared between all the households living in one apartment building at that time. The dominant archetype of the dial phone was replaced by the push-button telephone by the mid 1990s. In the past 5 years, more and more Chinese

urban families have removed their land line phones since nearly everyone now has at least one mobile phone, and are also enjoying the cheaper costs of calling through computer-internet phone systems. Out of our ongoing interview data collection, the following transcript illustrates the point.

I haven't used any dial-face telephone in real life for at least fifteen years! It was so interesting to use the dial-face telephone ... Da...da....da, I love the way we use it. I love this feeling... I remember when I was 8 years old, I often played with the dial-face telephone in my home, though my parents did not allow me to do so, because telephone was something very expensive at the time and not every family owned one, it was a home luxury... I miss the way I used to operate telephone, it reminds me of my childhood, when digital product is not everywhere, life was so simple and authentic... Yes, it's not efficient but I really would love one in my bedroom, maybe not original, but the dial-face is the most important.

Social interaction is the other important trigger of nostalgic experience under the interaction category, and it has a special current significance. A sense of belonging and meaningful social bonds are fundamental needs (Baumeister & Leary, 1995). But the increasing mobility and life transitions (e.g., graduating from high school, studying or working abroad, moving to another city) in modern societies perhaps inevitably lead to the impairment or termination of important traditional interpersonal relationships which can make people feel dispossessed and isolated (Colson, 1971). The role of social interaction (e.g., conversations with old friends from high school) in evoking nostalgic experience, embodies the interpersonal aspects of nostalgia and its function of enhancing social bonds. In terms of design, there are some products that may not be capable of triggering nostalgic experience either through appearance or usage, but by facilitating meaningful social interactions. One of most obvious cases is the social media. For example, Facebook enables people to find, chat and reconnect with the friends and they may have lost contact with for years or decades. In addition, people post, share and discuss their old photos and the memories to

make nostalgia a collective experience. Such social sharing of nostalgic episodes is an effective way to evoke nostalgic experience, and in turn the experience could help people to retain their identity, ease negative affects and increase the perceived ability to form, maintain, and develop interpersonal relationships successfully (Wildschut et al., 2006). It is a relatively new way of thinking for designers to design for nostalgic experience by enabling meaningful and nostalgic social interaction.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

Hopefully this paper will begin to provide the design community with a comprehensive understanding of what nostalgic experience is, what influences designing for nostalgic experience and what designers should perhaps consider when utilizing memory and nostalgia as a strategy.

Nostalgia is a universal human experience or affective state which is experienced by people from different age groups. Following the framework of product experience, we examine the nostalgic experience through three distinct components: (1) nostalgia as an experience of meaning, during which users' explicit memories or episodes are recalled; (2) nostalgia as a preference, an aesthetic experience, resulting from exposure to design phenomenon during one's critical developmental period, which may be explained by the retrieval of implicit memory; (3) nostalgia as an emotional experience, at this level, nostalgic experience is understood as a complex emotional response that involves both negative and positive emotions, but the proportion of positive components far exceeds that of negative ones. Nostalgic memory and experience can help individuals to retain their identities, ease any negative affects they are facing and enhance important social bonds. Subsequently, the users' age, gender, psychographic factors (e.g. personality and the attitude toward past), current affective state (e.g. mood) and context strongly influence the possibility and enjoyment of experiencing nostalgia evoked by interaction with a given product. Finally, sensory inputs and interactions are discussed as important design-related triggers of nostalgia. This discussion may help designers break the traditional confine of "nostalgic design only means looking old"

and tap some new possibilities of designing for other sensory inputs (e.g. olfactory and auditory) or interactions (e.g. operational interactions or social interactions) to design for nostalgic experience in the future.

FAMILIARITY AND NOVELTY

Design is always about making change, because invariably we are never completely satisfied with present conditions. The question is: should making change only mean bringing people new experiences? We often experience advertising as “...Our product provides people with a brand new experience...” and “novel”, ‘innovative’ or ‘original’ seem to be a highly positive words associated with the criteria of good design. It is perhaps true, that seeking new knowledge and experiences is a basic human need, but people also have a need for familiarity and security. Design and the development of technology are changing our material surroundings, behaviours and lifestyles continuously. When sufficient time has passed, we will feel, as the name of David Lowenthal’s book (1985) tells us, that “The Past is a Foreign Country”.

Figure 3. “The cassette in the past and present” as an illustration of the relationship between familiarity and novelty

A collective nostalgia associated with the “cassette and boom-box culture and experience” can be observed in recent design activities. Many people, including designers, miss the positive memories and experiences of physically pressing the mechanical play button on a walkman or boom-box, and being able to directly manipulate music and make mix-tapes for friends. Designers are therefore rethinking what we might have lost following the shift from analogue to digital products, and also how design could bring this cherished experience back to our present lives. For example, a new iPad App “Stereolizer” provides a lifelike imitation of the

analogue stereo operational interface from the 1980s on the touch screen. TDK, a formerly legendary cassette brand, meant music to music lovers in the 1980s and 1990s, but has lost its position in today’s digital world. The ZIBA design team created a new digital boom-box with many visual and interaction design cues from the cassette and old boom-box to revive the connections between TDK and music (O’Connor & Alviani, 2011). IDEO is also asking “what if we could physically touch our music again”. C60 Redux designed by IDEO aiming to bring back the physicality of music (Bone & Johnson, 2009).

What we see from these cases is that if designers could selectively review collective memories, they will be able to identify some valuable design influences (including interactive experiences) that have the potential to make strong emotional connections for users, but which do not yet exist or have not yet been incorporated within most of the objects that they are currently using. And when designers consciously employ these historical design influences to contemporary designs, integrate a missing familiar experience in the new product, and launch it in a completely different environment, it could be significantly differentiated from competing products and is very likely to provide users with both familiarity and novelty simultaneously. Accordingly, we argue that designers should consider users’ memories or previous experiences as an important inspirational tool. However, as with many design problems, a balance needs to be achieved between future potential, current need and past experience. A measured, creative and researched approach to nostalgia is therefore recommended in order to avoid simplistic design pastiche and an over-reliance on memory factors.

ETHICAL ISSUES

The ethical issues in nostalgic design should also be seriously considered. It is true that nostalgia is mainly viewed as positive and could help people overcome adversities, and that nostalgia may even contribute to both psychological and physical well-being. However, it may also result in some negative effects, such as losing interests in new opportunities or experiences if nostalgia was evoked excessively. As a result, to what degree nostalgia should be

evoked by design and how to produce suitably balanced design outcomes should be investigated as an important ethical issue in the future. In addition, in terms of environmental sustainability, design research could also examine how to avoid the short ownership cycles and disposable behaviour. A nostalgia evoking design strategy could well improve product attachment and lead to more sustainable product longevity and ownership.

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